

Health perceptions of the of physical Education and Sports Teacherin Promoting Health Awareness for Secondary School Pupils

-A Field Study in the Western Province of Algiers, Centre -

Latreche Aissam

I.S.T.A.P.S University of Bouira (Algeria)/Laboratory of Modern Sciences in Physical and
Sports Activities, a.latreche@univ-bouira.dz

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER RECEIVED : 11/07/2022 ACCEPTED : 15/10/2022 PUBLISHED: 01/12/2022</p> <p>KEYWORDS : Health perceptions ,Teacher of physical education and sports ,Health awareness, Secondary school pupil.</p>	<p>The study aims to identify the level of health perceptions of the teacher of physical education and sports and his role in promoting the level of health awareness for secondary school pupils. For this purpose, we used the descriptive approach on a sample consisting of (50) teachers and (340) pupils randomly chosen from the western province of Algiers, Centre. To collect data, the health perceptions scale and the health awareness scale were used. After collecting the results and treating them statistically, it was concluded that the level of health perceptions was just moderate while the pupils' level of health awareness was so high. On this basis, the study recommended the need to pay more attention to perceptions on the part of the teachers and the necessity to hold regular meetings for the teachers to discuss issues of health dimension.</p>
<p>Auteur correspondant : LatrecheAissam, e-mail: a.latreche@univ-bouira.dz</p>	

1. Introduction

Good health is central to human happiness and well-being as it contributes significantly to their prosperity, their wealth and even their economic progress. It is an essential factor in the development and stability of societies since health development is the backbone of the general development of societies. Health systems differ across most countries of the globe from one community to another and from one country to another. Therefore, we find the pattern and nature of the prevailing health philosophy is the decisive factor in determining the level of health and the extent of interest in this aspect.

Accordingly, developed countries pay great attention to the public health of their citizens by giving sports a great interest in society and preparing sports programs for the development of children and youth. These programs also depend on a number of factors that will achieve the goals of these countries, and among these factors are the functional abilities of each sample in order for it to have normal growth and development in terms of health " (Belkada, Ben Zidan, & Gazzal, 2020, p. 201).

Therefore, specialized scientific associations have encouraged community members to increase their daily movement and physical activity due to the significant importance of the regular practice of this type of activities for physical and mental health (Djerourou, Ben Zidan, & Ben Omar, 2020, pp. 252-253). On the other hand, we find that the current health problems are closely related to the wrong lifestyle adopted by the various groups of society, as the group of adolescents in schools is more likely to practice unhealthy behaviors such as: smoking, unhealthy nutrition, physical inactivity, which are the main source of the current diseases.

The World Health Organization (2011) affirms, "There is a close relationship between the low level of physical activity on the one hand and modern diseases on the other hand. Therefore, there has been an increased interest in preventing diseases through the practice of physical sports activities within educational institutions in order to improve students' health-related physical fitness" (Dahhoun, Ben Khaled, Attaallah, & Tahar, 2018, p. 85).

In this regard, it is necessary to adopt plans in order to change unhealthy behaviors and consolidate the principle of healthy behavior by adopting the approach of health education for young people through schools which

contain an important segment of society members. Health awareness is one of the necessary strategies that contribute to raising the degree of health stability through a sense of responsibility towards personal health and the health of others.

Al-Razhi (1999) indicates that improving the health status of the population and raising the level of public health for the individual and society is mainly related to the level of health awareness for the members of society(Alimami, 2008, p. 01).

The school is one of the most important institutions of social upbringing that is responsible for educating young people and one of the most important channels available to promote health. The fact that pupils spend almost a third of their day in school, the school provides them with various health knowledge and concepts that develop their talents in this regard and develop their awareness and perceptions concerning various health issues through most of the given programs and educational activities.

According to Casey and Christian (2003) , teachers have an important role in preventive and curative areas of school health by establishing an integrated set of concepts, principles, systems, and services which aim to enhance the health situation in schools and in societies.(Soltan & Salama, 2017, p. 393).

From this perspective, the teacher of physical education and sports is one of the main bodies in the field of education, due to his position which requires him to contribute to the education and training of pupils in various angles such as the health aspect at which physical education usually aims.

Pantler and Helen point out that the physical education and sports teacher has many responsibilities related to the pupils' health, which require more interest and preparedness on the part of the teacher in relation to health awareness.(Abduallah, 2017, p. 255).

Literature Review

Among the studies related to the current study, we find the one of (Gharib, 2013) entitled "The Level of Health Perceptions among Physical Education Teachers in the Sulaymaniyah Governorate Centre". The research aimed at identifying the level of health perceptions among physical education teachers specifically nutritional health and sports health. The researcher used the descriptive method and a scale developed by Muhammad Nasreddin Radwan and others (1998), which was slightly modified to suit

the Iraqi environment. The study sample consisted of (52) physical education teachers. The researcher reached several results, the most important of which was the existence of a difference in the levels of health perceptions and according to the items identified in the questionnaire, the level of perceptions among physical education teachers was quite good.

The study of (Harris, 2014) entitled “The perceptions and Experiences of Physical Education Teachers and their Role in Promoting Healthy, Active Lifestyles for Pupils in Secondary Schools” aimed to discover the impact of the perceptions and knowledge of physical education teachers on the lifestyle of pupils in secondary school through the interaction that occurs during the teaching -learning process. The descriptive approach was used and a questionnaire was administered to a sample of (124) pupils. The study concluded that the pupil’s knowledge about what a healthy and active lifestyle was very limited. In addition, their initial perceptions of learning related to promoting active healthy lifestyles in physical education were different from what they experienced in schools and there was no health-related education. Physical education teachers were ineffective in promoting healthy, active lifestyles, and had no idea of pre-defined health-related issues in teaching and learning.

- The study of (Green & Thurston, 2012) “Physical Education and Health Promotion” A Qualitative Study on Teachers’ Perceptions” which examined and discussed the extent to which promoting health awareness has become a feature of physical education and sports teachers and its direct impact on promoting health awareness among pupils. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive method was adopted and semi-structured interviews were conducted with (35) physical education and sports teachers from (17) schools in Northwest England. The researchers found that teachers repeatedly expressed their desire to encourage healthy and active lifestyles among pupils through physical education classes and most of them view health as the most important issue that all teachers should pay more attention to.

Therefore, research on this subject is more than necessary, especially in light of the modern global trends that have become focused on the role of schools in promoting health, and due to the critical role of the physical education teacher in promoting health awareness for young people. In addition, most of the similar studies investigated either the level of the health awareness of students, or the level of health knowledge of teachers. Thus, our study came to determine the health perceptions of teachers, as

well as the level of health awareness of students for the purpose of revealing the contribution of physical education to health promotion. Based on this perception, we proceed from the following research hypotheses:

- The health perceptions of the teacher of physical education and sports are not activated.
- The level of health awareness of secondary school students is low.
- The contribution of the teacher of physical education to promoting health awareness for secondary school students is inactive.

1. Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

According to Boudawood and Ata Allah (2009), the sample is defined as “A group of individuals that are taken from the original community so that they genuinely represent it” (Chennoufi, Ben Aki, & Ben Aki, 2020, p. 308).

The study sample, which was randomly selected, consisted of (50) physical education and sports teachers and (340) secondary school pupils for the academic year 2020/2021 in the western province of Algiers, Centre.

Materials:

In this current study, a scale of health perceptions designed by (Aissam Addin Mitouali Abdullah 2017) was used from which the researcher has taken three dimensions which were developed and adapted by the researcher to suit the Algerian environment.

Table 1: Description of the Health Perceptions Scale.

Dimensions	The dimension's objective	Number of items	Positive items	Negative items
Sports health	Examine the teacher's level of concepts and perceptions in the dimension of sports health.	07	04	03
Healthy nutrition	Examine the extent to which teachers control perceptions of nutritional health.	12	06	06
Prevention	Examine the extent to which teachers control preventive health perceptions.	12	08	04

Source: Prepared by the researcher.

Therefore, the overall score of the scale is (155) degrees, the minimum score is (31) degrees and the hypothetical average for the scale is (93) degrees

Table02: Scale correction method

Response Degrees	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Positive items	05	04	03	02	01
Negative items	01	02	03	04	05

Source: designed by the researcher

The second scale was designed by (Abdel-Tawab Jaber Ahmed Muhammad Makki 2017) on pupils' health awareness. The researcher has taken three dimensions which were: Sports health, healthy nutrition, and prevention. Finally, the scale was developed and adapted by the researcher according to the field of study and the Algerian environment in order to determine the level of health awareness for secondary school pupils.

Table 3: Description of the Health awareness Scale.

Dimensions	The dimension's objective	Number of items	Positive items	Negative items
Sports health	Examine the level of health awareness among pupils in the dimension of health sports	10	10	00
Healthy nutrition	Examine the level of health awareness among pupils in the dimension of nutritional health	10	10	00
Prevention	Examine the level of health awareness among pupils in the domain of prevention	10	10	00

Source: Prepared by the researcher.

The overall score of the scale is (90), the minimum score is (30), while the hypothetical average for the scale is (60).

Table04: Scale correction method

Response Degrees	Always	Sometimes	Rarely
Positive items	3	2	1
Negative items	1	2	3

Source: designed by the researcher.

Face Validity: Both scales were presented to a group of experienced and competent teachers for the purpose of expressing their opinions on the extent to which the tool is appropriate through the compatibility of the items of the scale and the field of study, as well as in terms of the linguistic wording and clarity in accordance with the Algerian environment.

The process ended up with the approval of the two scales with several remarks regarding changing and adding some items, changing response

alternatives and naming dimensions for the health perception scale. The percentage of agreement in the notes exceeded 90%, and after making the required adjustments, the two scales were represented again and were finally accepted for field application.

The hypothetical average was extracted according to the following method:

(Number of dimension items x upper scale response) - (Number of dimension items x minimum scale response) / 2 + (Number of dimension items x minimum scale response).

- The hypothetical average for the first scale = $(31 \times 5) - (31 \times 1) / 2 + (31 \times 1) = 93$.

- The hypothetical average of the second scale = $(30 \times 3) - (30 \times 1) / 2 + (30 \times 1) = 60$

- **Consistency:** consistency means obtaining the same results of the scale after repeating the process several times and on the same individuals. It also refers to internal consistency, so that each statement of the scale is consistent with the dimension to which it belongs (Bettaher, Akouche, & Saadaoui, 2019, p. 178). The consistency factor was calculated according to the following methods:

- **Test-Retest Method:** The two scales in their final form were applied on an exploratory sample of the study population estimated with (10) teachers and (30) pupils which was excluded from the basic study, and then we re-applied it again with a time difference of 08 days, on the same individuals and under the same conditions where the value of the stability coefficient was (0.) at the level of significance 0.01, which is considered a high value.

- **Cronbach's alpha Coefficient Method:** The consistency of the scale was also confirmed by calculating the Cronbach Alpha coefficient; its value reached (0.95) and (0.96) which is very high.

- **Intrinsic Validity:** The calculation of the validity of the scale also relied on the calculation of reliability, which equals the square root of the coefficient of consistency (Boukratem & Madani, 2019, p. 239). Thus, the value of reliability equals (0.95) and (0.97).

The obtained coefficients of consistency and reliability exceed the value of (0.70) which is very close to the value of (1). Therefore, both scales are consistent, valid and suitable for study.

Design and Procedure:

In order to define the objectives that the study seeks to achieve and in parallel with its nature, the descriptive method was used. According to Al-

Rifai Hussein (1996): “The method contributes to reaching accurate and detailed knowledge of the elements of the problem or phenomenon to reach a better and more accurate understanding, and it also aims to provide data and facts about the problem of the research to explain it and determine its significance (Benchaa, Chrit, & Khoudja, 2019, p. 204).

“ It Aims to study the phenomenon with all its characteristics and dimensions, in a specific context and analyzes it based on the data collected about it, then trying to reach its causes and the factors that control it, and thus reach generalizable results” (Zahaf & Maksoud, 2017, p. 322)

The independent variable: It is the main variable that affects the dependent variable and in our study it is the health perceptions of teachers of physical education and sports.

The dependent variable: It is the variable that follows the independent variable and is affected by it, and in this study it is health awareness.

The scale of health perceptions in the dimensions (sports health, healthy nutrition, and prevention) was applied to assess the level of teachers’ perceptions. To reveal the level of health awareness among pupils, the health awareness scale in the dimensions of (exercise, healthy nutrition, and prevention) was also applied.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

The data of the study have been quantitatively processed by the statistical software package for social sciences, spss version 22, by calculating the following equations:

-Percentages -Arithmetic average -Standard deviation.

There has been a comparison between the arithmetic averages and the hypothetical average for each scale.

2. Results

Results of the first hypothesis:

Table 3: Results of assessing the teachers’ level of health perceptions.

Health perceptions	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Hypothetical average	Percentage	Evaluation
Sports health	26.40	1.81	24	75.42 %	High
Healthy nutrition	33.90	1.25	36	51.58 %	Low
Prevention	35.75	2.24	36	64.58 %	Low
Total score	32.01	1.76	32	63.86 %	Moderate

Source: Prepared by the researcher.

On the basis of the data presented in the table above, which shows the results of “Assessing the level of health perceptions of teachers”, we notice that the value of the arithmetic average in the first dimension (sports health) has reached a value of (26.40) which is higher than the value of the hypothetical average (24), with a standard deviation of (1.81), The response rate was also estimated by (75.42 %). Therefore, it is clear to us that the teacher of physical education and sports in the secondary school possesses a high level of sports health perceptions, which are reflected positively in health awareness of pupils in this field. In the dimension of healthy nutrition, the value of the arithmetic average has reached (33.90), which is smaller than the value of the hypothetical average (36), with a standard deviation (1.25). Therefore, we conclude that the level of healthy nutrition perceptions of teachers is low, which is negatively reflected in the development of health awareness for pupils in this field. We also record in the prevention dimension that the arithmetic average has reached (35.75), with a standard deviation (2.24) which is smaller than the hypothetical average (36) and the response rate was estimated by (64.58%). This indicates that the level of preventive perceptions of the teacher is low, which in turn affects their role in promoting preventive health education of pupils.

Results of the second hypothesis:

Table 4: Results of assessing the level of health awareness among pupils

Dimensions	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Hypothetical average	percentage	Evaluation
Sportshealth awareness	24.30	2.93	20	80.98%	High
Healthy nutritional awareness	22.85	3.52	20	76.17%	High
Preventive health awareness	24.04	2.31	20	80.12%	High
Total score	23.73	3.25	20	79.09%	High

Source: Prepared by the researcher.

On the basis of the data presented in the above table, which shows the results of “Assessing the level of health awareness among students,” we notice that the value of the arithmetic average in the first dimension (sports health awareness) reached (24.30) which is greater than the value of the hypothetical average (20) and the response rate reached (80.98%). This confirms the high level of health awareness of pupils in this dimension,

while in the nutrition dimension, we record that the arithmetic average value reached (22.85) which is higher than the hypothetical average (20) with a standard deviation (3.52) and the response rate was (76.17%). This leads us to conclude the high level of nutritional health awareness among pupils. In the prevention dimension, we also record the high level taking into consideration that the value of the arithmetic average obtained (24.04) exceeds the hypothetical average (20) with a standard deviation (2.31), and with a response rate of (80.12%).

Results of the third hypothesis:

Table 5: The role of the physical education teacher's health perceptions in promoting pupils' health awareness.

Health perceptions	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Hypothetical average	Percentage	Evaluation
The level of teachers' health perceptions	32.01	1.76	32	63.86	Moderate
The level of pupils' health awareness.	23.73	3.25	20	79.09	High

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results obtained

By extrapolating the data in the above table, we note that the value of the arithmetic average of the overall score for the level of health perceptions is (32.01) which is approximately equal to the value of the hypothetical average (32) with a standard deviation (1.76) and with a response rate (63.86%). This indicates the average level of teachers in health perceptions. While we note in the level of pupils' health awareness that the value of the arithmetic average is (23.73) which exceeds the value of the hypothetical average (20) with a standard deviation (3.25) and with a response rate estimated at (79.09%). This indicates the high level of health awareness among pupils.

3. Discussion

- Discussing the results of the first research hypothesis:

Based on the collected data and the statistical analysis data contained in table (5) which represent the results of the first hypothesis, we concluded that the level of health perceptions among teachers is moderate. The researcher explains this result by the lack of cognitive knowledge among teachers of physical education, especially in the dimensions of "nutrition and prevention" due to the failure to expand the scope of access to the various sources of knowledge in this field, as well as the failure to keep pace

with the various developments taking place in this regard, as well as the teacher's' focus on the didactic aspect in teaching various programmed skills, and their lack of interest in obtaining health knowledge. Therefore, we confirm the first hypothesis.

The Findings of the current study differ with those of (Gharib, 2013), which concluded that the level of health perceptions among teachers was good. The study of (LAMANAUSKAS & AUGIENĖ, 2019) also found a broad understanding of health knowledge on the part of teachers. However, The present study is in line with (Harris J. , 2014), who concluded that the level of teachers' knowledge and health perceptions was low. In addition, the study of (Gudžinskienė & Česnavičienė, 2013) found that teachers lack sufficient knowledge about the prevention issues concerning many diseases.

Discussing the results of the second hypothesis

Based on the statistical analysis data presented in table (6), we note the level of health awareness among pupils is high. The researcher relates this result to the experiences they acquired from other academic courses, the various social institutions and the various sources of knowledge in this field, the role of health cultural publications through various means, especially electronic ones, as these sources positively affected the students in forming trends towards health awareness, which is positively reflected on their healthy lives and on society as a whole. Therefore, we reach to the point where we refute the second hypotheses.

The findings of the current study are consistent with the study of (Abdelkawi, 2019) and (Fadan & Boudouh, 2018) which concluded that the level of pupils' health awareness was high. However, this result differs with the study of (Harb, 2019), which concluded that the level of health awareness was just moderate. A study of (krishna & Rekha, 2018) also found that the level of health awareness among secondary school students was low. (Tamanal & Hoon Kim, 2020) concluded that the level of a healthy lifestyle is unstable in the study sample. The findings of (Almutairi, et al., 2018); indicate that the level of pupils' awareness of healthy life was weak.

- Discussion of the results of the second research hypothesis:

Based on the data obtained and on the statistical analysis data represented in table (07), we concluded that the role of the physical education teacher's health perceptions in promoting health awareness for pupils is not activated,

and the researcher relates this result to the ineffectiveness of the qualifications and the shrinkage of health cognitive competencies of teachers as well as their lack of interest in the field of health sciences and irresponsibility towards the mission they were entrusted to accomplish. Therefore, the researcher concludes with the confirmation of the second research hypothesis.

On the contrary, the findings of the study of (Green & Thurston, 2012), indicated that the role of physical education teachers is active in promoting health awareness of pupils. The study of (Alhalabi, 2017) reached a different result which indicated that the role of the school administration in developing health awareness was very high and effective. While the result of the current study is supported by the study of (Soltan & Salama, 2017) which concluded that the role of teachers in promoting concepts of health awareness was not satisfactory. This finding is also consistent with the one found by (Harris, 2014) who concluded in his study that physical education teachers have an ineffective role in promoting active and healthy lifestyle. A study of (Gray, Maclsaac, & Jess, 2015) found that the role of physical education teachers in developing and promoting health awareness was weak. The study of (Cheng & Wong, 2015) also found that the level of knowledge related to some health matters was generally less than average.

4. Conclusion

The issue of health awareness is one of the most important issues in society, and it is the basis for adopting a healthy lifestyle for members of society, so we cannot envision a healthy life for any community without being keen on knowing the health rules and basic information that contributes in raising the citizen's awareness level in this regard. Based on what has been done in this study, it became clear to us that the level of health perceptions of physical education teachers did not reach the required level and this should be a cause for concern.

In addition, the act of establishing health awareness for high school pupils is not encouraged by teachers of physical education and sports, considering them one of the actors in the field of education due to the close relationship between physical education and health. Therefore, the current study reached the following results:

- The level of health perceptions of the teacher of physical education sports was moderate.

- Physical education teachers lack control over health perceptions, especially in the dimensions of nutrition and prevention.
 - The level of health awareness among secondary school pupils was high.
 - The role of the teachers of physical education and sports is not activated in promoting the health awareness of secondary school pupils.
- In light of the findings, the researcher recommends the following:
- Physical education teachers need to pay attention to health perceptions, especially in the dimensions of nutrition and prevention.
 - Physical education teachers are required to pay attention to health education awareness for students.
 - Conducting similar studies and further expanding in the dimensions of health perceptions and health awareness.
 - Conducting similar studies on other levels of education.
 - The necessity to hold seminars and forums for physical education teachers to discuss topics related to health.
 - Conducting surveys on similar categories like teachers of natural sciences.
 - The need to organize scientific seminars by specialists in medical sciences to discuss the updates in the field of health.
 - The school administration should focus on establishing health awareness for pupils through various programs in the form of cultural activities, awareness campaigns, wall magazines...
 - The role of educational health media should be activated.

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